

**What makes your
Systematic Literature
Reviews Sustainable?**

Recording Consent

[REC]

- The meeting will be **recorded** and transcribed for research purposes.
- All data collected will be handled **confidentially**.
- Any published information will be fully **anonymized** to protect your privacy.
- Room setup and demographics will be recorded for **data analysis purposes**.

Agenda

- Introduction on Sustainability of SLRs (5 min).
- Key concepts presentation / examples (5 min).
- Discussion (50 min).

SLRs contains inefficiencies

Every decision = trade-offs/consequences

Sustainability dimensions

- **Economic** - involves all the resources (e.g., human time/effort, monetary, etc.) needed to build an SLR
- **Social** - involves all the concerns regarding communities (e.g., researchers, industry, etc.) that produce and consume SLRs
- **Technical** - involves all the infrastructure (e.g., guidelines, tools, etc.) needed to build an SLR
- **Environmental** - involves all the environmental impacts (e.g., energy consumption) caused by SLRs

Order of impact:

- **Direct (in SLR process)**
- **Enabling (after publication)**
- **Systemic (macro-level, behavioural change)**

Question

- What makes your SLRs sustainable?

We are looking for “lessons learned” or practices that make your research more sustainable.

In another words:

“Which **advices/tips** you would give for a friend/student that could make their research better (in any dimension)?”

We use the word “**sustainable**” in the broad sense.
Similar view of Software Engineering: multi-dimensional and systemic property.

Example of tactic...

Description

Economic - if the **researcher in SLR planning** calibrate **search strings** choosing the right keywords (**semantic filtering**) may **avoid irrelevant hits** that can be measured by **precision/recall ratio**, then the efforts to process this information will be reduced increasing **efficiency**.

The model for tactics

Example of tactic...

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The model for tactics

Let's Discuss!

Step 1

1- What *practices (intent)* you adopt to make your SLRs more sustainable?

Frame the “practices” as advices that you usually adopt to improve your SLRs in any dimension: economically, socially, technically or environmentally.

Focus: the intent

Let's Discuss!

Step 2 - for each practice (intent)

1- What is the *target quality attribute* being addressed?

2- What are *other related quality attributes*?

3- Which *measures* the intent should adopt for target QA?

Focus: measures & quality attributes

Let's Discuss!

Step 3 - for each practice (intent)

1- How you can achieve each intent?

- Who participate?
- In which context (*SLR phase)?
- Which artifacts (*Inputs/outputs) are involved?
- Which features (*action/task)?

Focus: how to achieve the intents

Next Steps

- We may contact you if further clarifications are needed
- We will share with you the draft of the results

Thanks a lot!